

Analysis of motor units activity to study stiffness modulation in humans

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Abstract—Finding a control method for variable stiffness myoelectric prostheses, which outperforms all others, is still an open topic in research. In this work, the technique of Motor Units decomposition of EMG signals is investigated in order to extract the neural information content transmitted through motor neurons in the form of Motor Units Spike Trains. The hypothesis is that there is a certain co-ordination between the Central Nervous System and Motor Units, which can be detected by coherence analysis of the Cumulative Spike Trains extracted from a pair of antagonistic muscles, and which allows an exclusive signal for stiffness control to be found. This hypothesis is tested with a pilot study by analyzing the EMG signals recorded from the biceps and triceps muscles of a healthy subject during tasks that involve varying the stiffness of the elbow joint.

Index Terms—Stiffness, Motor Units, Prostheses

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there's been intense interest in improving upper limb prosthetic control, aiming to replace uncomfortable body-powered prostheses with ones that can interpret the user's biological signals. These latest devices rely on electromyographic signals from muscles and they are called myoelectric controlled prostheses. Challenges include finding robust, simple, and intuitive myoelectric control techniques. What seems to be truly helpful is a thorough study of the behavior and organization of the Central Nervous System (CNS) to determine the processes underlying EMG signals and maximize the utilization of obtainable biological information. In this regard, more recently, research has begun to extend beyond the mere signal resulting from muscle contraction, and interest is growing around the activity of motor neurons. In parallel with these developments there has been an inquiry into the possibility, and consequently the utility, of creating upper-limb prostheses with variable stiffness. This idea arises from the study of the human musculoskeletal system [1], which indeed exhibits different behaviors during specific situations and tasks. The primary focus of this work is to investigate how the CNS controls stiffness.

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Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the control of a pair of antagonistic muscles

Based on previous studies [2] [3], the cross-correlation analysis between the mean firing rates of the concurrently active MUs in the two antagonist muscles that control the interphalangeal joint of the thumb, showed the presence of common fluctuations with peaks in time zero, revealing essentially zero time-shift between them. These results led to some very interesting speculations such as the existence of a co-activation command common to both muscles and the fact that the nervous system acts on the motor neuron pool in a uniform manner. More recently, it was thought that a broader picture could be reached by extending correlation procedures into the frequency domain using coherence analysis [5]. This technique is the one adopted in this study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental Setup

This pilot study involved a young and healthy male subject. The equipment used was: a Biodex Dynamometer System, 4 HD sEMG grids of 64 channels and a Quattrocento amplifier by OT Bioelettronica. Two grids were specially placed to record the biceps activity, while the other two the triceps activity. The entire setup is shown in Figure 2. The EMG signals were sampled at 2048 Hz and digitally filtered between 20 and 500 Hz with a Butterworth filter.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup

B. Experimental Protocol

The experiment was split in two protocols.

- Protocol 1: The aim was to investigate the MU activity underlying different levels of elbow stiffness during flexion-extension movements. The subject had no feedback on EMG activity. He was asked to perform 3 reps of isometric contractions following a trapezoidal reference at 10%, 20%, 30% of his MVC with torque feedback for biceps and triceps activation. After assessing fatigue the protocol was repeated for a total of 5 times.
- Protocol 2: The aim was to investigate the MU activity underlying different levels of elbow stiffness during isometric contraction. The subject had visual feedback on the coactivation level and was asked to modulate it. A Stiffness Index was defined as the average of the envelopes of the two EMG signals of the antagonist muscle pair. The participant was asked to maintain 10%, 20%, 30% of the maximum coactivation during isometric contractions following the same trapezoidal reference as in the first protocol.

C. Coherence Analysis

Coherence analysis is an extension of Pearson's correlation coefficient to the frequency domain and indicates precisely the linear correlation between two signals for different frequency values. Generally, this type of analysis is divided in between-muscles and within-muscles depending on whether spike trains of different muscles or of the same muscle are taken into account [6]. It is applied on two sets of Cumulative Spike Trains of the same size generated by the sum of the spike trains to study. In addition, another type of analysis found in the literature [7] is the one called pooled partial coherence. In this case, the objective is to estimate the proportion of specific input received by a muscle by eliminating the components synchronous with the neural drive of the other muscle.

III. RESULTS

Decomposing the dataset through the algorithm described in [8], proved to be particularly challenging. The identified spike trains displayed unevenness (Figure 3). Additionally, the analysis through Spike Triggered Averaging reveals non-physiological waveforms, indicating potential misidentification of discharge times. Given the problems listed, it was not possible to reach relevant conclusions. This work highlighted

Fig. 3. Decomposition results showing the activity of a single MU

the difficulties in achieving a reliable MU decomposition of the EMG signals recorded from the biceps and triceps muscles. This is probably due to the geometric muscle structure and the arrangement of MUs, for example in pennate muscles the fibers are oriented obliquely relative to the tendon and this creates a more complex spatial distribution of EMG signal sources. Furthermore, the high density of fibers increases the overlap between the signals of different MUs making it harder to identify them. Nevertheless, the choice of the muscle group was linked to the aim of this paper of studying the stiffness modulation of the elbow joint in relation to the control of a variable stiffness elbow prosthesis.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Although prosthetic mechanical design has achieved architectures capable of modulating stiffness, EMG control techniques remain simplistic. MU decomposition could provide new information, including signals representing stiffness modulation intent. In this pilot study the decomposition of EMG data into MUs was very complex and made it difficult to arrive at statistically significant conclusions. The experimental protocol should be revised in the future works involving different antagonist muscle pairs.

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